

Original Research

Enhancing Compliance and Governance: Role of Internal Control Units in South Africa's Department of Rural Development and Agrarian

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Received 26 January 2025 Revised 1 June 2025 Accepted 11 June 2025

Abstract

This study examines the effectiveness of the Internal Control Unit (ICU) in promoting compliance and governance within the Eastern Cape Department of Rural Development and Agrarian Reform (ECDRDAR). Grounded in communication theory, which emphasizes the role of clear, structured messaging in ensuring compliance and organizational efficiency, the study explores key challenges undermining ICU effectiveness. These include inadequate communication of compliance procedures and undue pressure on ICU staff to process non-compliant transactions. A quantitative cross-sectional survey approach was employed, gathering data from 150 finance and ICU staff through purposive non-probability sampling and interviewer-administered questionnaires. Descriptive statistics and correlation analyses revealed significant relationships between communication gaps and instances of non-compliance ($r = 0.95$, $p < 0.05$). The findings underscore critical operational gaps within the ICU, emphasizing the need for enhanced training, clearer policy dissemination, and organizational safeguards to mitigate undue pressure on ICU personnel. By addressing these challenges, government departments can strengthen compliance mechanisms, improve governance, and enhance service delivery. This study contributes to the literature by examining the ICU's role within public service, offering practical insights for policymakers and departmental leadership in reinforcing internal control systems.

Keywords: Communication theory, compliance and governance, internal control unit, public service delivery, South Africa.

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Introduction

ICU is a unit established to assist the finance function with compliance of the Public Finance Management Act (PFMA) provisions, procurement related legislation, policies and processes when the department renders public services, as such the unit is incorporated within the departmental finance structure (Treasury regulation, 2001). It is a statutory provision that ICU must monitor and ensure compliance with the PFMA provisions, procurement related legislations, policies and processes when the department renders public services (Department of National Treasury, 2012). This unit pre-audits procurement processes when the department acquire goods and services to ensure all procurement related legislations, policies and procedures are upheld. It also pre-audits all payments process to confirm their compliance with the PFMA payment guidelines before the payments are authorised. Lastly, the unit identifies financial risks, weaknesses such as non-compliance with the PFMA provisions and recommend areas for improvement to the management. Thus, establishment of ICU is necessary as essential internal control mechanism as a tool for monitoring, and ensuring control activities are upheld (Tys, 2015). It provides reasonable assurance that all rules and regulations are adhere to regarding internal control activities (Coetzee, et al., 2014). Further enhancing operational compliance within departmental operations.

Based on the above, the role of ICU in enhancing compliance with internal financial controls and governance has reaped increasing consideration. Despite its recognized importance, evidence suggests that inadequate communication of compliance procedures and undue pressure on ICU staff to process non-compliant transactions significantly undermine the effectiveness of ICUs. This situation is relevant within the context of ECDRDAR, where Audits by the Auditor-General South Africa (AGSA) frequently highlight irregular, fruitless, and wasteful expenditures due to non-compliance with procurement laws and financial policies (Geqeza, 2019). The department often fails to effectively communicate financial policies and compliance expectations to employees, leading to inconsistent adherence to regulations. Poor dissemination of compliance guidelines results in confusion and procedural errors. Although anecdotal evidence is abundant, empirical research examining the effects of inadequate communication of compliance procedures and undue pressure on ICU staff to process non-compliant transactions on ICU effectiveness within the ECDRDAR context remains limited (Geqeza, 2021).

Additionally, communication theory has not been widely used to examine the role of ICUs in government departments, particularly in ensuring compliance and governance, constraining our understanding of the underlying mechanisms (Chakabva, Tengeh & Dubihlela, 2021). By applying this theory, research provides new insights into how communication influences compliance behaviour in public administration. Furthermore, this study helps to bridge both the theoretical and empirical gaps by integrating communication theory into the analysis of ICU effectiveness and offering new empirical insights into compliance challenges within government departments. This enhances understanding and informs policy recommendations for improving governance structures.

Given the above, a guiding question that underpinned this article was as follows:

How do communication gaps and organizational pressures impact ICU effectiveness in enforcing compliance?

Literature Review

Theoretical and Conceptual Background

Communication theory

Effective communication is essential in a variety of circumstances, particularly in a multicultural workplace (Abdullah, 2010). This process allows employees in the department to interact and operate successfully and efficiently. According to Carr, Holman, Stephenson-Abetz, Koenig Kellas and Vagnoni (2015) the widespread use of modern technologies in the workplace, the global nature of organizing and the changing person-organization interaction, all highlight the importance of effective communication in the workplace because it contributes to workplace success. Acts, interactions, and double interactions are the three types of communication behaviour that combine to advance conversational objectives (Cornelissen, 2014). As a result, it is fascinating to uncover these socially taught communication patterns that occur in any organization.

Given the importance of communication at work, experts have focused on competency and success in corporate communication. Communication theory focuses on how individuals use messages to construct meaning inside and beyond contexts, cultures, channels, and compliance, to attain the fundamental aim of comprehension (Summers, 2014). Communication theory guides the research design by shaping variable selection, data collection methods, and respondent sampling. It also informs the interpretation of findings by explaining how communication breakdowns impact compliance and governance. Ultimately, the study contributes to governance reforms by recommending enhanced communication strategies to improve compliance adherence.

Application of Communication theory in this study

Communication is at the heart of all organizational strategies since it involves not just interactions between management and personnel, but also efficient communication inside an organization. Communication theory was recently identified as a method for communicating within the organization (Linjuan, 2014; Odine, 2015; Omilion-Hodges & Baker, 2014). This theory is essential in understanding how information flow, messaging, and feedback mechanisms impact compliance and governance within government departments, particularly in the ICU of the ECDRDAR. According to Van Ruler (2018) communication cannot occur without the transmission of a meaning and individuals create and employ meaning in their interpretation of events. Similarly, communication is a vital tool that is used within ECDRDAR to disseminate information and messages conveying compliance processes. Communication aids decision-making, a fact noted by the information and communication component of the Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission (COSO) Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) framework of 2004. Therefore, it is necessary that accurate, timely and up-to-date information reaches all ECDRDAR' employees and decision-makers so that they can successfully carry out their respective responsibilities (Chakabva, 2020).

In the same vein, communication from sources both inside and outside the ECDRDAR is used to circulate crucial information both internally and externally when necessary to reply to messages and satisfy departmental needs and expectations (COSO, 2019). Similarly, communication from sources both inside and outside of the ECDRDAR is used to circulate crucial information internally and externally, ensuring timely responses to messages and alignment with departmental needs and expectations. The ECDRDAR internal flow of information also enables senior management to show staff members the importance of control processes (COSO, 2019). The internal flow of information allows senior management to show the relevance of control systems to employees, promoting a culture of accountability and compliance. However, unlike departments in countries with more sophisticated e-governance systems—such as Estonia or New Zealand—ECDRDAR's communication strategy lacks a strong digital feedback loop or real-time compliance dashboards, which are becoming recognized global best practices (OECD, 2021).

For example, the World Bank (2020) found that ministries in Singapore and Denmark use integrated digital communication technologies to automatically distribute updated policies and highlight control violations in real time, significantly lowering noncompliance. In contrast, ECDRDAR's reliance on manual circulars and hierarchical information channels puts significant "noise" into the communication process, as developed by Shannon and Weaver's (1949) model, resulting in message delays or distortions that can threaten compliance. Furthermore, while COSO highlights the need of good internal communication in maintaining control environments, the ECDRDAR case exemplifies how incomplete communication flows, without reciprocal feedback systems, might limit staff engagement in control activities. This contrasts with the findings of a South African National Treasury research (2018), which found that two-way communication between leadership and ground-level staff in departments such as Health and Education resulted in improved compliance outcomes. This analysis, by contrasting the ECDRDAR's communication approach with global and national case studies, not only extends the COSO framework but also contributes to a deeper theoretical synthesis, emphasizing the critical role of flow less communication, digital tools, and horizontal communication in strengthening internal controls and promoting compliance.

Communication audit is an element of communication theory. According to Tourish & Hargie (2017), communication audits assist firms to identify their internal communication hurdles and offers solutions for guaranteeing efficient channels of communication. Communication auditing seeks to identify specific issues within an organization's internal and external communication environments. A communication audit, according to Smith (2017), is a deliberate research methodology that analyses the organizational strengths and shortcomings of its internal and external communication systems. The communication audit also reveals communication gaps within an organization to decision-makers, thereby allowing them time to consider the information before making a deliberate choice of action (Besterci & Hazel, 2014).

The communication of compliance procedures is one of the communication theory's ideas (Ikiseh, 2020). Practically, apart from rendering assurance services, ICU staff's renders, also provide advice to the management. Another skill that is necessary for ICU to complete their professional responsibilities is the capacity to communicate

(Mulyandini, 2023). This requirement is because during the audit engagement, the auditor is constantly in communication with the auditee. According to Hogard and Ellis (2006), this connection is aimed at fostering good cooperation for the compliance process to be successful. It is also important to recognize that ICU and auditees are individuals with distinct features, behaviours and habits that are manifested in their conduct. When there is conflict in the interaction between the ICU and the auditee, that could prevent the compliance process from going smoothly, the ICU need to have a solid understanding of human behaviour.

To tackle such a situation psychologically and more effectively through communication, an ICU must have specialized knowledge or abilities, thus, in this case effective communication skills become vital (Tourish & Hargie 2006). It is hoped that ICU will comprehend and gain knowledge of the actions and communication strategies that can be used to build rapport with the party being audited (Hogard & Ellis, 2006). When performing their professional duties ICU must establish a comfortable environment for the auditee. The ICU's empathy may serve as an entry point for the auditee's openness in factfinding (Saiewitz & Kida, 2018). According to Kent, Munro and Gambling (2006) auditors must be able to motivate themselves to acknowledge their own efforts and the hard work they put into their professional duties. This practice is necessary for the ICU to communicate effectively and maintain self-control when interacting with the auditee. According to Sarapaivanich et al., (2019) success in audit assignments is largely dependent on a variety of factors, including the ICU's physical appearance, skills and knowledge, social graces, communication talents, the ability to understand the psychology of the auditee, and leadership qualities. An ICU must first comprehend and the tasks to be performed before constantly developing and maintaining self-control when interacting with auditees to increase her/his professionalism (Raiborn & Stern, 2019).

Additionally, the auditor must work to establish contact and cooperation with the auditee and attempt to comprehend the auditee's conduct. Government departments are institutions whose capital is wholly contributed by the state through taxpayer's money. To safeguarding taxpayer's money and communicating departmental status through financial statements, ICU were established in government departments. The ICU must know how to properly communicate with the taxpayers and what information is crucial for the government to know or be aware of. However, according to Wijayati (2023) they are frequently repeating the same auditing findings in their audit reports. These results are hampered by a lack of communication during audits (Masdan et al., 2017). Communication is critical in the compliance process since it is the first step for the ICU to express its professional responsibility to the auditee. The ICUs well-developed contact with the auditee will promote a seamless operation in finding and assessing the required compliance process (Hogard & Ellis, 2006).

Barriers to communication theory

Effective internal controls rely on clear, accurate, and timely communication of compliance procedures, financial policies, and regulatory requirements. According to Shannon and Weaver's Communication Model (1949), communication breakdowns (e.g., unclear messages, misinterpretation, or noise) can result in misunderstandings, leading to non-compliance. when compliance procedures are not properly communicated to

employees, errors, inefficiencies, and even fraudulent activities may occur. Similarly, a qualitative study by the Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA, 2019) discovered that 48% of compliance violations in surveyed organizations were caused by employees not fully understanding internal policies due to insufficient training and poor policy documentation—both classic examples of "noise" in communication according to Shannon and Weaver's frameworks. Auditors discovered that certain middle managers at a South African financial institution failed to implement Anti-Money Laundering procedures because policy updates were distributed via overly technical email memos without interactive clarification sessions or managerial reinforcement.

In a qualitative study by Kabuye, Kato, Akugizibwe and Bugambiro (2019) on internal controls in Ugandan SMEs, it was found that “employees lacked a full understanding of control policies due to inadequate training and ambiguous documentation.” This led to repeated procedural errors and non-compliance with tax and regulatory requirements. Moreover, in the 2021/2022 audit report by South African Auditor-General, for example, 75% of municipalities had findings related to compliance and internal control deficiencies, often due to improper dissemination of regulatory requirements. The reports consistently identify weak control environments and poor communication of financial policies as major contributors to irregular expenditure and non-compliance in municipalities. Similarly, there are barriers to effective communication that defeat the purpose of communication theory within the ECDRDAR, (Ikiseh, 2020). These barriers stem from over-reliance on written memos, emails, or policy documents without interactive training or clarification sessions. Inadequate feedback mechanisms, where employees cannot seek clarification or report challenges in applying compliance procedures. As a result, unclear financial policies create ambiguity, making it easier for officials to justify irregular spending or bypass internal controls (Patako & Yazdanifard, 2014).

Communication hurdles can arise from both managers and employees, obstructing or distorting the true meaning of a message and stifling clear, open, and satisfactory communication in the department (Ikiseh, 2020). According to various researchers (Agarwal & Gary, 2012; Conrad, 2014; Rani, 2016) there is also a risk of message overload, lack of response and physical challenges, all of which impede successful communication. Message overload normally occurs when a person receives an excessive amount of information in one message. Physical obstacles include the nature of the surroundings, that might result in environmental problems such as physical noise over which the department has no influence. Unwanted interference, primarily linked with message delivery, is one of the environmental elements that impact efficient communication inside the department. Also, the lack of feedback or not knowing who to report to instance, have an adverse impact on effective communication inside the department. Noise and a lack of input, for example, can harm the department. Lastly, these barriers constitute a hindrance that prevents the ICU and management from successfully transmitting information, ideas and messages about compliance procedures (Rani, 2016).

Effects of audit Communication on compliance process

Communication is critical for ICU since compliance entail the process of obtaining and transmitting information required to accomplish compliance. In this aspect, the ICU, at the very least, could influence the auditee's psychological state. Among other issues, the psychological atmosphere of the interaction offers a friendly, safe environment in which the auditee feels welcomed in delivering the information required concerning the facts of irregularities discovered by the ICU (Tourish & Hargie, 2006). The term 'communication' is derived from the Latin word *communis*, that means "making togetherness or building togetherness between two or more people" (Mulyandini, 2023). According to Sarapaivanich (2019) communication serves as a conduit for enacting and receiving the effects of compliance processes, a tool to promote more motivation, as well as an intermediate way for an organization to accomplish its objectives.

The auditee, who is the client in this instance, is contacted at the most advanced level during the audit. The ICUs are guided by departmental legislations and internal controls to always have an objective mental attitude. However, according to Kent et al. (2006) the auditee's psychological characteristics also influence the ICU's effectiveness. According to Sarapaivanich et al. (2019), communication style and psychological comfort have an impact on how much people trust ICU services. To accomplish corporate goals, Hogard & Ellis (2006) argued that effective communication during compliance is essential. A technique that combines effective communication within the institution to accomplish institutional goals involves the quality of communication between management, personnel, and the ICU (Tourish & Hargie, 2006). According to Dinda and Suryandari (2021), to generate sound conclusions and make workable suggestions from the information exchanged during an audit, the ICU need to have effective communication skills. Audit communication can obtain the data required for compliance testing, while ICU psychology can comprehend the auditee's behaviour, attitudes, and leadership styles (Mulyandini, 2023).

Research Methodology

The study targeted the head office and seven district offices of the ECDRDAR. Prospective respondents were selected using a purposive sampling method. This was because the study only wanted employees that possess sufficient knowledge and experience in ensuring compliance with financial regulations (Surbhi, 2016). To qualify, respondents needed to have worked within the ECDRDAR ICU for at least two years and possess auditing qualification. The final sample consisted of 150 ECDRDAR ICU employees (made up of Clerks, Officers, Senior Offices, Assistant Directors and Deputy Director). The sampled employees completed and returned the questionnaire resulting in 100% response rate. However, this subjective selection method can introduce bias if the criteria are poorly defined or if certain population characteristics are overlooked. Additionally, purposive sampling, by its nature, may result in a sample that does not fully represent the broader population, potentially limiting the generalizability of the findings. Despite these limitations, the sample size of 150 employees can be considered representative of the target population, as it significantly exceeds the minimum of 30 recommended for quantitative studies (Eichler et al., 2018).

Data Analysis

To minimize data collection bias, the researcher ensured that all respondents met the specified selection criteria. The questions like: “are you working within the ICU” and “how long have you worked within the ICU”, were asked to ensure compliance with the established criteria. Subsequently, 150 interviewer-administered Likert scale questionnaires were distributed to the selected sample, all of which were fully completed and returned for analysis. Questionnaire pre-testing was done by pre-selecting respondents and request them to complete the questions. This was to confirm whether the questionnaire attains what it was intended. The reliability and validity of the measuring instruments was done using Cronbach’s Alpha and correlation analysis. The collected data was analysed using SPSS software, and the results were presented in the form of descriptive statistics.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical clearance was obtained for this study. The researcher respected the privacy of the respondents by not disclosing to anyone, the personal information that is attained. The data was stored on cloud, where it could only be accessed by the researcher. Respondents were told that the data gathered would be used only for scientific purposes and would never be shared with anyone who is not personally interested in the contents of this research report.

Descriptive Sample Means

Three central measures, median, mean, and standard deviation were used to summarize the study's findings. As noted by Gravetter and Wallnau (2013), the mean is commonly employed to rank or prioritize items, while the median provides insight into the central or middle value. These measures formed the basis for interpreting responses on a five-point Likert scale. Specifically, a mean value of 3 represented a neutral or "moderate" response, values greater than 3 (4 and above) indicated agreement, and values below 3 signified disagreements. Table 1 presents the mean score ratings for the five variables analysed.

Table 1: Factors impeding ICU effectiveness

Factors	1	2	3	4	5	Total agreement
Inadequate communication of compliance procedures	9%	19%	13%	36%	23%	59%
Undue pressure on ICU staff to process non-compliant transactions	18%	13%	0%	46%	23%	69%
Employees lack adequate training	6%	10%	32%	43%	9%	52%
Lack policy clarity	6%	14%	18%	40%	22%	62%

Reliability and validity of the results

The study employed construct validity. The reliability of the survey results was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha. According to Morgan and Waring (2004), data

reliability involves ensuring that data is collected accurately, comprehensively, and appropriately to measure the intended concept. Cronbach's Alpha was employed to evaluate the extent to which different variables in the questionnaire consistently measure the same concept. The survey instrument achieved an internal consistency reliability score of 0.70, indicating 70% reliability. The reliability test results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Cronbach's Alpha values for the reliability test

Constructs	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's alpha based on standardized items
ICCP	.929	.932
UPICU	.935	.939
ELAT	.796	.816
LPC	.862	.863

NOTE: ICCP= Inadequate communication of compliance procedures; UPICU= Undue pressure on ICU staff to process non-compliant transactions; ELAT= Employees lack adequate training; LPC= Lack policy clarity.

Kerlinger and Lee (2000) state that reliability test results with values of 0.60 or higher are considered acceptable and indicate reliability. In this study. Based on these alpha values, it was concluded that the data is reliable.

Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis was performed to evaluate the validity of the survey results. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was used to examine the linear relationships within the data and to determine the statistical significance of the relationships between variables. The first construct assessed was the objective of the ICU's role, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Inter-item correlation table for Factors impeding ICU effectiveness

Correlations						
	Means	SDV	ICCP	UPICU	ELAT	LPC
ICCP	4.21	.802	1			
UPICU	4.29	.86	.708**	1		
ELAT	4.34	.707	.586**	.440**	1	
LPC	4.37	.788	.615**	.420**	.563**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)
 NOTE: ICCP= Inadequate communication of compliance procedures; UPICU= Undue pressure on ICU staff to process non-compliant transactions, ELAT= Employees lack adequate training; LPC= Lack policy clarity

The inter-item correlations analysis for each construct above was conducted to establishing the relationship amongst the constructs. The result indicates a positive moderate to a strong correlation to each other at 95% significant level ($p= 0.01$).

Findings

The results indicated that there is an inadequate communication of compliance procedures and undue pressure on ICU staff to process non-compliant transactions, employees lack adequate training and lack policy clarity. These findings may align with existing theory in the following ways: Shannon and Weaver's Model of Communication (1949). This classic model describes communication as a linear process involving a sender, message, channel, receiver, and potential noise (barriers). The study's findings support this model by showing that: Compliance procedures are not clearly communicated (message distortion). Barriers (noise)—such as bureaucratic complexity, unclear policies, or lack of training—disrupt the transmission of compliance information. Feedback mechanisms (opportunities for staff to seek clarification) may be weak or absent.

These findings may challenge existing theory in the following ways: Traditional governance and compliance models assume that organizations operate rationally, with clear policies and accountability mechanisms. The study reveals that even when compliance procedures exist, their miscommunication or manipulation (via pressure on ICU staff) creates irrational decision-making and non-compliance. Many compliance frameworks assume that strong policies automatically lead to compliance (e.g., PFMA & Treasury Regulations). The findings suggest that policies alone do not ensure compliance; effective communication and protection from undue influence are also necessary.

Research Implication

The issue of inadequate communication of compliance procedures and undue pressure on ICU staff to process non-compliant transactions can be analysed through communication theory and its management and organizational implications as follows:

Communication Theory Perspective

The findings—inadequate communication of compliance procedures and undue pressure on ICU staff to process non-compliant transactions—offer both theoretical and practical contributions to the fields of communication theory, compliance, and governance.

Contribution to Communication Theory

Reinforcing the Role of Effective Communication in Compliance: The study confirms that clear, accessible, and structured communication is essential for ensuring compliance with financial regulations. This aligns with Shannon and Weaver's (1949) model of communication, where message distortion ("noise") can lead to misunderstandings in compliance procedures.

Application of the Transactional Model of Communication

The study highlights the need for continuous feedback loops in compliance communication. The absence of proper two-way communication creates uncertainty, misinterpretation, and ultimately, non-compliance. This supports the Transactional Model of Communication, which emphasizes that both sender and receiver actively shape communication outcomes.

Communication Barriers and Organizational Power Dynamics

The finding that ICU staff face undue pressure to approve non-compliant transactions introduces a power dimension to compliance communication. This aligns with Critical Communication Theory, which suggests that hierarchical structures and power imbalances influence communication effectiveness.

Contribution to the Broader Literature on Compliance and Governance

Bridging the Gap Between Policy and Implementation: Governance and compliance frameworks (e.g., COSO Internal Control Framework, PFMA) assume that compliance is primarily a procedural issue. The study challenges this assumption by demonstrating that even when procedures exist, poor communication and organizational pressure undermine their effectiveness. This calls for a behavioural and communicative approach to compliance—ensuring that regulations are not just documented but understood and reinforced.

Expanding the Understanding of Compliance Failures: The broader literature often attributes non-compliance to lack of training or technical capacity. This study shifts the focus to organizational culture, showing that even knowledgeable ICU staff may approve non-compliant transactions due to pressure from superiors. This supports and extends Agency Theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976), which states that agents (ICU staff) may face conflicting incentives imposed by principals (management).

Implications for Strengthening Governance in Public Sector Organizations: Weak internal controls and ineffective compliance communication contribute to financial mismanagement in government departments. The findings reinforce the need for: Stronger compliance communication strategies, including interactive quarterly training on PFMA compliance and clear reporting channels. Whistleblower protections to shield ICU staff from retaliation when they refuse to approve non-compliant transactions. Independent oversight mechanisms to reduce undue influence on ICU staff.

Management Implications

Training Deficiencies: Inadequate communication suggests insufficient training programs, leaving ICU staff unprepared to enforce compliance procedures effectively.

Ethical Concerns: Pressuring staff to process non-compliant transactions may create ethical dilemmas and undermine the organization's integrity.

Performance Impact: Miscommunication or lack of clarity can reduce staff efficiency and effectiveness, as employees struggle to align their work with compliance standards.

Departmental Implications

Reputational Risk: Failure to communicate compliance procedures properly can lead to regulatory violations, which may damage the organization's reputation.

Employee Morale: Undue pressure on staff fosters stress, dissatisfaction, and potential burnout, affecting overall morale and productivity.

Systemic Weakness: Persistent communication failures might indicate deeper structural issues within the department, such as poor leadership or lack of standardized communication channels.

Policy Recommendations

To improve communication and reduce pressure on ICU staff, the (ECDRDAR) should implement the following targeted interventions:

Strengthening Compliance Communication

Develop Clear Compliance Guidelines & Standard operating procedures: Ensure that all compliance procedures are documented in simple, accessible language. Distribute a compliance manual to all relevant staff.

Use Multiple Communication Channels: Implement regular training workshops on PFMA compliance, emails, online portals, and in-person briefings to ensure all staff understand compliance expectations. Create a dedicated internal communication platform (e.g., intranet, WhatsApp group) where ICU staff can ask questions and receive updates on compliance procedures.

Enhance Two-Way Communication: Encourage ICU staff to seek clarification without fear of retaliation. Implement a feedback loop, where employees can report unclear procedures anonymously.

Reducing Pressure on ICU Staff

Implement Clear Escalation and Reporting Mechanisms: Establish a formal, confidential reporting system for ICU staff facing pressure to approve non-compliant transactions. Ensure independent oversight committees review complaints and take corrective action.

Introduce a No-Retaliation Policy: Enforce whistleblower protections for ICU staff who report compliance breaches. Conduct regular audits to identify and address instances of undue pressure.

Decentralize Decision-Making: Reduce the direct influence of senior officials on ICU staff by: Assigning an independent compliance officer to oversee critical decisions. Rotating ICU staff to prevent undue influence from specific individuals.

This multi-faceted approach aligns communication practices with organizational goals to mitigate risks and enhance operational efficiency.

Limitations of the study and avenues for future research

While this study provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of Internal Control Units (ICUs) in ensuring compliance and governance within the ECDRDAR, several limitations should be acknowledged.

Potential Bias from Purposive Sampling

The use of purposive sampling ensured that only employees with relevant experience and qualifications were included. However, this subjective selection method may introduce bias when: Certain perspectives within the broader ICU staff population were overlooked. Employees with diverse compliance experiences (e.g., junior staff, external auditors) were excluded. As a result, the findings may not be fully generalizable beyond the sampled population.

Limitations of a Cross-Sectional Design

The study employed a cross-sectional survey, which captures data at a single point in time. This limits the ability to: Establish causal relationships between communication effectiveness, compliance behaviours, and governance challenges. Identify long-term trends or changes in ICU effectiveness over time. A longitudinal study could provide deeper insights into how compliance challenges evolve and whether interventions improve compliance outcomes.

Self-Reporting and Response Bias

The study relied on self-reported data from ICU employees, which may be influenced by: Social desirability bias—respondents may have overstated their compliance efforts or downplayed governance challenges. Perceptual differences—some employees might interpret compliance procedures differently, affecting response consistency. Future studies could incorporate triangulation methods (e.g., financial audits, compliance reports, interviews) to validate self-reported data.

Generalizability Constraints

While the sample of 150 respondents is statistically robust, the findings may not fully apply to: Other government departments with different compliance structures. Provincial or national-level compliance frameworks beyond ECDRDAR. Further research could expand the sample to multiple departments to enhance external validity.

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